

The Taller de Prácticas Docentes [Teaching Practice Workshop], a Role-Playing-Based Proposal for Higher Dance Studies

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Abstract: This study focuses on current developments in Higher Dance Studies in Spain. The proposal for a Taller de Prácticas Docentes [Teaching Practice Workshop, or TPD by its Spanish acronym] carried out at the Higher Dance Conservatory of Alicante (Spain) and implemented as a pilot experience at this centre became our research point of reference. A learning space was designed in the TPD for the purpose of familiarising students with a type of experiential learning through role playing. Furthermore, a controlled classroom atmosphere was created seeking to encourage the habit of reflexive action in the future of Dance teaching. This research was based on both a case study and a mixed approach. The methodological proposal put forward through the TPD is based on the analysis of experiences as well as their impact on those involved in them, especially with regard to the reflections by teachers and students. Findings confirm that the TPD appears as an innovative process which helps students develop their capacity to be reflexive professionals. This is why the TPD was eventually included in the Conservatory's Official Curriculum after its experimentation.

Introduction

Our historical roots have long established the choice of Dance teachers based on the exclusive criteria of professional success. Their artistic experience, technical mastery and professional experience made them ideal candidates to teach (Warburton 2002, 2004). This conception has always oriented us towards the development of a teaching model where teachers organised and directed the whole technical training – mostly confined to dance practice and body learning – with very few opportunities for chances of intervention (Morris 2003; Pickard 2012; Tembriotti and Tsangaridou 2014).

The social changes experienced over the last two decades show the growing popularity of leisure and recreation habits based on movement and Dance amongst the population as a whole. This new reality takes us away from the criteria of the traditional-technological model and towards the need for an emphasis of initial teacher training focused on the development of professionals who can make a contribution to the training process of our citizens, either artistically or socially. This means becoming familiar with new parameters which are in tune with the model based on teaching inquiry – also known as ‘critical perspective method’.

All the considerations above inevitably lead us to approach the initial training of a Dance teacher pursuant to the criteria that define a reflexive professional, who considers that the knowledge about teaching practice needs to be generated from the trainee teachers themselves. Professional reflexive practice refers to the way in which teachers undertake the commitment to facilitate and handle challenges associated with their profession, namely: artistic creation; curriculum; and artistic pedagogy (Burnard 2006; Tembriotti and Tsangaridou 2014).

As suggested by Burnard (2006) and also by Pimentel, Coutinho, and Guimarães (2009), both thinking and reflexive judgments become essential when it comes to arts and their creative processes. Artistic creation requires intellectual processes which can orient the creative process and suitable conditions which encourage responsibility on the basis of commitment and willingness towards the environment taking into account its cultural and social consequences. And all this, pervaded by a natural attitude full of intuition as well as reflection, characterises the creative process (Hennessy 2006).

Reflexive practice is an ongoing professional development process that materialises in an attitude and ability inherent to teacher status (Perrenoud 2004). It is advisable to introduce a reflexive attitude in the initial training of a Dance teacher through practical experience, either in direct

contact with reality or through simulation (Perrenoud 2004; Zabalza 2003, 2011). The experiential model – where knowledge is generated as a result of simultaneously ‘capturing and transforming experience’ (Kolb 1984, 41) stands out as one of the most highly recommended ones. The Higher Dance studies developed in Spain (Higher Dance Degree) which specialise in Dance pedagogy, Choreography and Interpretation, correspond to level 2 (grade) of the Qualifications Framework for the European Higher Education Area (QF-EHEA), as laid down by Royal Decree 96/2014, of 14 February.

This dance educational level has a short historical-legislative tradition. Its curricular design was established by the Organic Law 1/1990, of 3 October, on the Overall Regulation of the Educational System (LOGSE by its Spanish acronym, developed in Royal Decree 1463/1999 of 17 September, whereby the basic aspects of the curriculum for the Higher Dance Degree are established, and Decree 128/2002, of 30 July of the Valencian Regional Government, which establishes the curriculum for the teaching of the Higher Dance Degree in the Valencian Autonomous Region), and subsequently modified by Organic Law 2/2006, of 3 May, on Education (LOE by its Spanish acronym, developed in the Royal Decree 632/2010, of 14 May, which regulates the basic content of higher artistic studies in the Higher Dance Degree and in Order 25/2011, of 2 November, of the Regional Department of Education, Training and Employment, which establishes and authorises syllabuses for centres (dependent on the ISEACV) imparting the higher artistic Dance studies leading to the Dance Degree.

This study focuses on Higher Dance Studies currently taught in Spain, and more specifically, on the speciality of Dance Pedagogy mentioned earlier. It is our intention to carry out an in-depth examination of the proposal for a Taller de Prácticas Docentes [Teaching Practice Workshop, (TPD, by its Spanish acronym)], which developed between the 2007/08 and the 2011/12 academic years, as an innovative process within the subject of External Teaching Practices. It was carried out by the teachers in charge of developing this curricular subject at the Higher Dance Conservatory of Alicante. Subsequently, from the 2013/14 academic year, and following the results of the research presented here, the TPD was incorporated as an independent subject (Taller de Prácticas Internas [Internal Practice Workshop]) in the fourth year during the modification of the curriculum carried out to adapt these studies to the European Higher Education Area (EHEA) in the speciality of Dance Pedagogy (Order 25/2011, of 2 November, of the Valencian Autonomous Region).

The study was originally motivated by the desire to solve certain difficulties associated with the development of external teaching practices spreading outside the Conservatory. Nevertheless, its scope was extended after its implementation. Indeed, a learning space had been successfully created which allowed students: (a) to become familiar with teaching practice from within the classroom’s-controlled environment; (b) to spread reflexive processes; and (c) to study the personal and social coexistence of various dance registers (classical; contemporary; and Spanish). All the above is promoted from a proposal format and structure based on the active participation of each learner, always in harmony with the class group. Students must make their own decisions individually, as that will allow them to become protagonists in their own learning, while teachers remain in the back ground. These aspects and characteristics reflect the methodological premises established in the EHEA. That is why these suggestions appear as suitable training environments for the teacher trainee’s skill development before the curricular developments in Higher Dance Studies (Decree 48/2011, of 6 May, of the Valencian Autonomous Region), and have been included in the new curriculum of this Autonomous Region (Order 25/2011, 2 November, of the Valencian Autonomous Region). This study consequently aimed at examining the methodological proposal applied in some of the experiences carried out in the TPD, along with its impact on participants (students and teachers). This allowed us to identify the extent to which the TPD adapts to the training space emerging from the new curriculum.

The proposal sought to make teachers familiar with reflexive practice, transversally, across each one of the subjects included in the curriculum. The intention was to experiment, research and

build comprehension and reflection processes. The TPD made it possible to bring together the three dance disciplines included in the Dance Pedagogy speciality at the time – classical; contemporary; and Spanish. The purpose was to experience a specific type of teaching practice, from within the classroom's controlled environment, and oriented to reflexive processes additionally connected with social and disciplinary coexistence. The TPD thus emerged as a participatory methodology in the format of a horizontal workshop (Ander-Egg 1999) meant to promote an experiential type of learning (Castillo and Cabrerizo 2005b; Kolb 1984; Kolb and Kolb 2005; Perrenoud 2004; Schön 1998; Zabalza 2003, 2011) and based on the role playing technique (Clapper 2010; Joyce and Weil 2002; López and Población 2011).

This experience led to the following research questions:

- (1) How was the TPD proposal received by participants (teachers and students)?
- (2) How did the TPD methodological process permit and favour the construction of processes focused on reflection and intercommunication between the various dance techniques amongst teachers?
- (3) What advantages and drawbacks were detected after developing the TPD?

Answers to these research questions would provide insights into ways of developing correct practices for trainee teachers in the Dance Pedagogy degree, since despite their importance the studies available on this topic are scarce. Our approach when it comes to generalisation must be cautious, though, since this is a case study.

Method and Procedure

We decided to follow a qualitative methodology for an in-depth analysis of the educational phenomenon through participants' perceptions. The instruments used to collect information were narratives based on participant observations while engaging in their three roles, and open-ended or semi-structured questionnaires. The software used for the treatment of data and their subsequent analysis was the AQUAD (Analysis of Qualitative Data) program, version 6.6 for qualitative data treatment (Huber and Gürtler 2004).

The research was undertaken following the guidelines provided by the methodological complementariness approach which, according to Mengual (2011), facilitates the understanding of a research problem 'because it is possible for the researcher to pay attention to multiple objectives that can arise in the context of a single research' (126). Similarly, Cook and Reichardt (1979), as well as Murcia and Jaramillo (2001), consider that multimethod makes possible a better analysis of the phenomenon under study when it comes to studying educational phenomena. Therefore, the present study adopted a qualitative, multi-method research in terms of data collection (Albert 2009). As for the research qualitative design, we decided to follow the cases established by Flick (2004), the interpretative paradigm (Imbernón 2012), and finally the 'teacher's thinking' line of research (Imbernón 2012; Sandín 2003) focused on the active agents of the teaching-learning process, namely: expert teachers and teacher trainees.

Because our research interest revolved around the actual proposal, we chose a case study of an intrinsic (Stake 1999) and interpretative nature (Merriam 1998). In fact, the interest of our research focuses on the proposal itself, which provides abundant information derived from its development and implementation with the participants that will serve as an interpretative basis for the understanding of the phenomenon under study and the achievement of the aims set for the research work. Furthermore, carrying out both workshops placed us within the parameters of a case study with sub-units, in turn interpreted as a collective (Stake 1999) or a multiple (Merriam 1998) case study. Such studies provide the research with more consistency and robustness and become consolidated as more convincing ones (Rodríguez, Gil, and García 1999).

The context was the Higher Dance Conservatory of Alicante (Spain), in the 3rd and 4th years of the 'Dance Pedagogy' subject and the experiment began in the 2007/08 academic year. That experimentation served as the basis to introduce improvements and to define the final TPD model, included during the 2013/14 academic year as a subject in the curriculum for the new degree. The sample was selected in a non-probabilistic way and by availability (Cardona 2002),

as the board, staff and students were asked for their respective permission to carry out the research. The participants were 3 female lecturers with recognised experience in the context of dance training, as well as (n = 4) a specialist in contemporary dance; another specialist in classical dance; and two specialists in Spanish dance. As for learners, there were 11 women from each one of the selected years, 3rd and 4th (n = 22).

With regard to the procedure, the research developed in three stages (Stage 1, Stage 2, and Stage 3) which represented different moments within the workshop from which data were collected using diverse instruments. The aim of the first stage consisted in collecting information on the willingness both of learners and of teachers to implement the TPD, on its organisation, and on the implementation of different dance techniques. An open-ended questionnaire with both participant sectors – students and teachers – as its addressees served to achieve this purpose (Rodríguez, Gil, and García 1999) prior to the start of the TPD. The second stage corresponded to the specific development of this workshop, in the course of which an effort was made to collect information about its evolution. Learners played three roles during this second stage:

- (1) as a student, being the addressee of another classmate's teaching action;
- (2) as an external observer, objectively reflecting on another classmate's teaching practice; and
- (3) as a teacher, developing two sessions of a Didactic Unit (DU) designed by them.

Narrative reports were actually drawn up after the implementation of the aforesaid DU (McMillan and Schumacher 2005), where they could highlight the difficulties found in its preparation and implementation. To give an example, if the student who performs the teaching role belongs to the classical dance area, he or she teaches students from the contemporary and Spanish dance disciplines who play the student role, and their classmates of the same discipline (classical dance) assume the observer role. They subsequently exchange roles.

The analysis of the various documents prepared for each role provided the data which were analysed during this second stage. Finally, our aim in the third stage focused on knowing (becoming aware of/collecting) the participants' final impressions about the implementation of the TPD. Once again, the open questionnaire for learners and teachers' final reports about the workshop helped to obtain information with regard to such assessments.

Results, Analysis and Discussion

Stage 1: Expectations before implementing the TPD [...]

Inquiry about students' opinion before implementing the TPD

A detailed reading of the information obtained from the initial questionnaires provided a list of categories and codes which were defined, interpreted and assigned to their corresponding text segments to give them greater meaning, producing the results shown below (Table 1). The same process took place in each one of the projects that the present research consists of.

Table 1. Overall results: Inquiry about students' opinion prior to the implementation of the TPD.

Category	Findings					
	3rd year	4th year	Both years	Third	Fourth	Total
1. Initial vision of the proposal	8.33	11.97	10.27	19	31	50
2. Positive expectations towards the workshop	32.46	32.05	32.24	74	83	157
3. Negative expectations	2.19	3.09	2.67	5	8	13

towards the workshop						
4. Benefits of other techniques in teacher training	19.74	10.42	14.78	45	27	72
5. Need for training in other techniques and their body contribution	37.28	42.47	40.04	85	110	195
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	228	259	487

Category 5. Need for training in other techniques and their body contribution obtained the highest representation with 195 findings, which accounts for 40.04% of the total of 3rd and 4th year, followed by category 2. Positive expectations towards the workshop, where participants perceived the initiative positively 157 times (32.24%), as shown by the following reflection:

I believe that not only knowledge of Classical Dance is necessary to complete the professional training of a dancer or teacher, but also the practice or the knowledge of other disciplines such as Contemporary or Spanish Dance so that they can help us increase our own knowledge, which will undoubtedly improve our practice as teachers, since this broadens the scope of our contributions to students as well as our awareness of the work carried out. (A-PRO-ALUM.08)

Inquiry about teachers' opinion before implementing the TPD

In the case of teachers (Table 2), the category with the highest number of references (47) was 7. Need for training in other techniques and their body contribution (36.15%), which gathers opinions linked to the need for training in other techniques, an aspect on which both students and teachers agree:

Even so, I would like to highlight that the knowledge of other specialities favourably enriches any speciality, achieving an interconnection of contents which makes any teacher's approach more broad-minded, [and] transmitting that knowledge to students during the teaching-learning process. (A-PRO-DOC.01.)

Both results make it clear that the proposal generated positive expectations amongst the participating teachers and students, mainly focused on appreciating the benefits that they can receive from training in dance techniques other than those included in their specialisation, and the development of teaching skills from three dimensions:

- (a) *Professional*, based on the possibility of becoming familiar with teaching action and its reflection, which is in keeping with the proposals made by Perrenoud (2004) and Castillo and Cabrerizo (2005b), according to whom the teacher's role fits that of professionals who reflect on their own practice and are not only ready to change but can also be self-critical – these being aspects which need to be developed in initial teacher training from proposals that can integrate such factors – ;
- (b) *Social*, through the interaction with other technical options, sharing and coexisting with 'his doing and his thinking?' – thus coinciding with the ideas of Ossoona (1984) and Lipman (1997); and
- (c) *Personal*, related to the body practices that they were going to experiment, which, in the opinion of participants, could contribute to the actual improvement of body movement and favour processes of reflection on their own practice. This type of experience can therefore

help teachers develop critical thinking skills with regard to the motor and expressive process, as suggested by Leijen (2009).

Table 2. Overall results of the a-2 Project. Inquiry on teachers' opinion before implementing the TPD.

Categories	% of presence	Findings
1. Initial vision of the proposal	10.77	14
2. Positive expectations of the student towards the Workshop: teacher's opinion	19.23	25
3. Negative expectations of the student towards the Workshop: teacher's opinion	3.85	5
4. Positive expectations about the Workshop for teachers	8.46	11
5. Negative expectations about the Workshop for teachers	2.31	3
6. Benefits of other techniques in the teacher's training	19.23	25
7. Need for training in other techniques and their body contribution	36.15	47
Total	100.00	130

Table 3. Results about the student's reflection from his participation in the *student role*.

Reflections in student role (A-2 Reports)						Findings	Total
	3rd year	4th year	Both groups	Third	Fourth		
1. Reflections on teaching practice from the student role	15.79	14.42	30.21	69	63	132	
2. Contributions to teacher training	9.38	7.78	17.16	41	34	75	
3. Artistic contributions	5.03	6.18	11.21	22	27	49	
4. Body contributions	16.70	15.10	31.81	73	66	139	
5. Social and personal contributions	5.03	1.37	6.41	22	6	28	
6. Reflections on the workshop	2.29	0.92	3.20	10	4	14	
Total	54.23	45.77	100.00	237	200	437	

Stage 2: Expectations during the implementation of the TPD

Our purpose in this second stage was to identify the training that the TPD offered to learners when performing their three roles: student role, observer role and teacher role.

Students' reflections about their participation in the student role

Category 4. Body contributions referenced 139 times (31.81%) appeared as the one with a greater presence (Table 3), a result which stresses the markedly positive character of practice in other disciplines. This can be explained by the chance to study other body languages as well as to widen the knowledge of other disciplines through their practice, which in turn favours future collaboration, relationship and understanding between teachers who may take different options but simultaneously remain members of the same teaching team:

It is great for us to receive classes of other disciplines, since it increases our knowledge and allows us to apply what it offers us to our own discipline. (B-PRO-A2.15)

With regard to category 1. Reflections on teaching practice with 132 references (30.21%) – slightly below the category with the highest presence–, it could be suggested that the student role position makes the process of reflection on teaching action easier in the sessions developed by the classmates who work under the teacher role, analysing aspects such as: collaboration; innovation or tradition in the approach to session structures; the teaching tools exposed; the interest in exploring the teaching practices of other disciplines, etc.

It follows from the above that the first results are in keeping with those of the stage preceding TPD implementation as well as with those obtained by other authors – Warburton (2002, 2004) and Leijen (2009), to quote but two – insofar as these actions offer the possibility of developing reflections on their experimentation and body learning through a boost to students’ critical thinking skills and the analysis of their motor and expressive response. This role allows learners to focus their observation not only on the visual or auditory perception that they perform in relation to the teacher’s action but also on the personal experimentation that they receive from that action; and, according to Sanmartín (2003), every sense is involved in this process, since students are in contact with the reality observed.

Students’ reflections on their participation in the observer role

Participation in this role aimed at introducing learners into a process of reflection observing teaching practice with the purpose of identifying relevant aspects of teacher-student interaction externally amongst learners (Table 4).

Table 4. Results for student’s reflections on his participation in the observer role.

Category	Observer role reflections			Findings		
	3rd year	4th year	Both groups	Third	Fourth	Total
1. Teacher role observation	36.62	51.23	44.42	78	125	203
2. Student role observation	30.52	17.62	23.63	65	43	108
3. Contributions of technical codes	10.33	15.98	13.35	22	39	61
4. Reflections on the workshop	4.23	4.51	4.38	9	11	20
5. Reflections on the observer role	14.08	4.92	9.19	30	12	42
6. Interdisciplinary reflections	4.23	5.74	5.03	9	14	23

Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	213	244	457
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The reflections on teaching action, grouped into Category1. Teacher role observation with 44.42% of the references obtained (203 findings) concentrated all the aspects and elements related to the knowledge factor and the didactic factor within teacher-student communication, that is to say, on what to communicate – and how to communicate it.

This whole reflection has proved especially useful for me when it comes to revising and appreciating the theoretical knowledge applied to sessions, such as methodology, the timing of session activities and the resources utilized, amongst other aspects. It can consequently be said that, being an observer, I was able to extract positive elements for my own training as a future (female) teacher from every experimented session, both from the things which turned out to be good for the teaching-learning process and from those which were not that good. (B-PROY-O3.08)

The observer role allowed students to become familiar with reflexive processes focused on the teacher's figure and on the actions performed by the latter, analysing aspects such as how to get student attention and to introduce tasks, along with feedback and reflexive processes. For Bandura (1987), this role turns students into observers of other people's experience, which they subsequently use in their own learning process through the investigation and reflection mechanism – what Zabalza (2003) calls 'reflexive observation skill' from the postulates of experiential learning developed by Kolb (1984).

Students' reflections on their participation in the teacher role

The third role performed by students throughout the TPD corresponds to the teacher role, in which they developed two sessions of a previously established schedule. Their implementation allowed learners to write three narrative reports which gave rise to three projects that had as their respective objectives:

- (a) the difficulties found when preparing Didactic Units (D3 Report);
- (b) the implementation of scheduled sessions (D4 Reports for the first session and D6 for the second one); and
- (c) the teacher's behaviour in the classroom, reflected in the D5 (first session) and D7 (second session) reports.

Table 5. Results of D3 Reports-Reflections carried out on the design and preparation of Didactic Units.

Categories	Findings					
	3rd year	4th year	Both years	Third	Fourth	Total
1. Planning of didactic units	18.45	19.56	38.01	50	53	103
2. Preparation of didactic units	21.40	29.15	50.55	58	79	137
3. Difficulties with ICTs	0.00	0.74	0.74	0	2	2
4. Student role reflections	5.17	5.54	10.70	14	15	29
Total	45.02	54.98	100.00	122	149	271

D3 reports – reflections carried out on the design and preparation of didactic units

The highest number of reflections accumulates in category 2. Preparation of Didactic Units (Table 5), with 137 references in both groups (50.55%) that transmit all the reflections expressed by learners on the drawbacks and doubts arising before the adoption of decisions for the preparation of the aforesaid units. One participant expressed it as follows:

(...) nevertheless, I think session time distribution is the aspect where we faced the most difficulties when preparing didactic units – since we only had forty-five minutes to inform, warm-up, develop and finish – and, after seeing the development of the first session, a correction will possibly have to be made for the second one. (B-PRO-D3.21)

Category 1. Planning of Didactic Units, which was present 103 times (38.01%), informed us about the aspects considered by learners in their initial planning stage, where they had to make decisions about the organising axis of units, based on the adaptation to the group's specific context and characteristics – very disparate in this case.

In the light of the above, it could be established that the preparation of these reports helped learners start situated reflection processes from the preparatory stage of the teaching action, making a contribution to their training process and skill development.

D4-D6/D5-D7 reports, issued by students from the teacher role, 1st and 2nd session

Based on Table 6, the analysis and comparison of learners' reflections on their practice in the teacher role in both sessions shows us that category 4. Teaching behaviour, has been the most commonly referenced one in both sessions and both groups (63.06% in the 1st session, with 942 findings; and 63.64% in the 2nd one, with 575). Such data suggest that their intervention as teachers allowed them to develop the ability to analyse and reflect on their own action, and also that it responded to their interest in mastering some classroom skills. More precisely, the greatest interest focused on the code which referred to the knowledge of results, as shown by the following comment:

Table 6. Overall results for categories in both sessions.

Category	1st session			2nd session		
	3rd year	4th year	Both years	3rd year	4th year	Both years
Analysis about the implementation of the didactic unit prepared	16.77	15.61	32.38	15.30	16.85	32.15
Reflection on the design of didactic units	1.06	1.80	2.87	1.22	1.44	2.66
3. Reflections on the teacher role	1.49	0.21	1.70	1.22	0.33	1.55
4. Teacher behaviour	29.72	33.33	63.06	28.16	35.48	63.64
Total	49.04	50.96	100.00	45.90	54.10	100.00

Work was carried out on different levels during the session process, so that the information was being prepared as the activities developed regardless of where the latter took place; thus, information was given before the beginning of the activities in order to explain the aim that I wanted to achieve; during

their development, to warn about corrections or focus the attention on some specific feature, and also at the end of the activities, to explain my assessment about the activity performed. (B-PRO-D4.10)

The second most valued one is category *1. Analysis about the implementation of the Didactic Unit prepared*, with 32.38% in the 1st session and 32.15% in the 2nd one. This leads us to conclude that learners seek the connection with other disciplines, the body-related and cognitive contributions standing out amongst their proposals.

The detailed study of aspects such as teaching behaviour and the implementation of planning allows us to verify that it all forms part of a process of inquiry and reflection-criticism about the planning of an action and about the action itself, where female students have become involved through their participation in the development of the TPD. All this is regarded as a necessary process to ‘accredit an evolution towards their professionalisation’ (Perrenoud 2004, 46). This makes possible a second most elaborate intervention, equally followed by its reflection. Direct practice and its reflexive process are therefore activated from this experience (Castillo and Cabrerizo 2005b; Dewey 2007; Perrenoud 2004; Schön 1998; Zabalza 2003, 2011).

Stage 3: Information collected after implementing the TPD

The purpose of this stage consisted in carrying out an inquiry about the TPD’s final outcome. To that end, our attention focused on: the training value which had been perceived in the proposal, the effects of its organisation and planning, as well as the convenience – or not – of its continuity, both from teachers’ and from students’ point of view.

Students’ final questionnaires

Analysing the data contained in Table 7 leads us to highlight that the presence of category *1. Positive aspects of the workshop* accumulates 56.08% of the total number of findings obtained (415), thus stressing the improvement that students achieved in their professional training after their participation in the TPD:

This whole experience has forced us to deeply reflect on various aspects related to our action as teachers and students and about the behaviour of the other female classmates within those same roles, which in turn has exerted an influence on us when trying to improve our own educational intervention. And neither can it be forgotten that this work has proved very useful to ‘refresh’ much of the knowledge acquired over these years. In short, as I already said in the answer to the previous question, it was a positive as well as enriching experience. (C-PRO-ALUM.09)

With regard to category *2. Negative aspects detected in the Workshop*, with 14.32% of the total number of findings (106), opinions suggesting excess work prevailed:

Table 7. Overall results obtained from the interpretation analysis about students’ final questionnaires.

Category	Findings					
	3rd year	4th year	Both years	Third	Fourth	Total
1. Positive aspects of the workshop	25.07	31.17	56.23	185	230	415
2. Negative aspects of the workshop	7.72	6.64	14.36	57	49	106
3. Personal feelings about the workshop	2.44	3.66	6.10	18	27	45
4. Proposals for improvement	4.74	3.12	7.86	35	23	58
5. Continuity	1.63	2.17	3.79	12	16	28

6. Disciplinary opinion	5.83	5.83	11.65	43	43	86
Total	47.43	52.57	100.00	350	388	738

In principle, the negative aspect of this workshop is the ongoing task of having to draw up reports about each one of the sessions every week, even though the truth is that it represents a way to pose yourself many more questions and it makes you reflect on these sessions which have already been performed. (C-PRO-ALUM.02)

In the light of the results above, it can be established that learners mostly make a positive assessment of the proposal after its experimentation, highlighting its most relevant characteristics from three dimensions which emerge in the course of category coding: the professional one, followed by the social and the personal one.

The analysis from a professional point of view (Castillo and Cabrerizo 2005b; Dewey 2007; Kolb 1984; Perrenoud 2004; Schön 1998; Zabalza 2003, 2011; Zeichner 1993) reveals:

- (a) the chance to carry out previous training for teaching practice, covering the whole process that this entails (planning, organisation, action and feedback for their action); and
- (b) an opportunity to become familiar with constant reflection processes that cover the whole development and permit to manage improvements for the next session; hence their capacity to set up an ongoing link between theory and practice.

From a social dimension (Bowman 2008; Davies and Lowden 2007; Joyce and Weil 2002), the analysis has a twofold outcome too:

- (a) it promotes collaborative participation through the interaction of all three roles; and
- (b) it integrates the technical-dance interdisciplinary relationship, thanks to connections between body and didactics across Dance registers present in the TPD, and based on the difficulty to manage them, thus encouraging empathy and tolerance (Lipman 1997).

Finally, from the personal dimension:

- (a) it favours a positive attitude towards initiatives of this kind (Kolb and Yeganeh 2012): students assume responsibility for their learning and, consequently, learn to manage their work in an autonomous way (Kolb and Yeganeh 2012); and
- (b) it additionally promotes the acquisition or widening of knowledge related to other dance disciplines both at a body level and in terms of theory.

Although they do not emerge strongly, it is indeed worth highlighting categories

4. *Proposals for improvement* (7.86%), associated with the organisation of the proposal, and 5. *Continuity*, with (3.79%), from which it follows that the TPD should be introduced as a curricular area because of its suitability to start an initial experimental phase for the teaching practices developed in these studies or the extent to which it promotes good dance judgement (Leijen 2009; Warburton 2002, 2004).

However, this does not prevent us from taking into account that excess work stands out amongst the aspects seen as inadequate, arising in both the personal and social dimensions.

Teachers' narratives (end-of-year reports)

The overall results obtained come from analysing and interpreting opinions expressed by teachers in their final reports (Table 8); category 2. Positive aspects detected in the TPD, accumulates 40.46% of the total contributions with 70 findings. In their explanations, teachers placed the emphasis on the development of teaching skills, which includes aspects related to classroom management and organisation, along with the personal contribution received, as shown by this teacher who expresses his gratefulness for the opportunity to encourage collaborative work:

Furthermore, the Workshop largely contributes to develop a series of teaching and dance skills from which I extract some listed in the Draft Dance Degree that the team of the Higher Dance Conservatory of Alicante submitted to the MEC (Spanish acronym for Ministry of Education and Science) in September 2007. We have successfully implemented the first collaborative model at our centre. (C-PRO-DOC.03)

The TPD therefore makes teamwork possible, providing an opportunity to implement the EHEA active methodologies where the teacher works in the background and becomes a teaching-learning process facilitator (De Miguel 2006). These conclusions are in tune with other research works about similar experiences carried out in higher education university contexts (La Spina 2011; Martínez Riera 2009).

Nevertheless, teachers also highlight a number of negative aspects detected in the workshop: category 3, with a presence of 13.87% of all findings. Teachers stressed the workload that they had to assume before, during and at the end of the TPD, as well as the inappropriate initial timing, which caused problems to students. The reflection below can serve as an example:

When it starts, there is a negative attitude because of the additional work volume, but over time, and on the whole, all the (female) learners consider it interesting, as shown at the end of the Workshop – this being the assessment that really matters. The process during the workshop is also the usual one. Learners are thus reluctant, but they work all the same. Moreover, execution during the first semester triggered certain negative reactions towards the development of this workshop amongst students. This was due to their lack of knowledge needed to draw up the reports required for its development. (C-PRO-DOC.01)

Discussion and Conclusions

The partial results, argumentations and conclusions of each stage allow us to draw answers to our research questions:

How was the TPD proposal initially received by participants (teachers and students)?

After analysing the results obtained in the first research stage, it can be concluded that the proposal generated a high degree of interest and trust amongst participants. Nevertheless, signs of insecurity appeared which most probably had to do with the innovative character of this proposal and its social and multidisciplinary interaction. All of this is in tune with the proposals made by Ander-Egg (1999) with regard to the utilisation of the workshop format; by Zabalza (2003) about the requirements to take part in experiential learning; or by Davies and Lowden (2007) in relation to the use of the role playing technique.

Table 8. Overall results for all the categories obtained from the interpretation of teachers' final reports.

Category	% of presence	Findings
1. Final vision of the proposal	15.03	26
2. Positive aspects detected in the workshop	40.46	70
3. Negative aspects detected in the	13.87	24

workshop		
4. Proposals for improvement	10.98	19
5. Continuity	6.94	12
6. Favours skill development	12.72	22
Total	100.00	173

How did the TPD methodological process permit and favour the construction of processes focused on reflection and intercommunication between the various dance techniques amongst teachers?

The TPD proposal sought to make participants aware of the benefits brought by reflexive practice, elaborating on other similar proposals (Castillo and Cabrerizo 2005a; Perrenoud 2004). In this regard, it has indeed encouraged participants' reflexive practice, as shown by the results obtained in the 2nd and 3rd Stage. The partial conclusions drawn during those stages highlight the fact that the TPD introduces us into three moments of teaching reflexive practice: previous phase; action phase; and feedback phase. It can thus be stated that this workshop experience gave a boost to reflexive practice amongst participants, allowing learners to make the experiences their own and to see them from the three roles that they perform therein. It simultaneously favoured the acquisition of tools for awareness-raising, understanding and appreciation of the various situations, elements and functions which shape teaching action, together with the connection between theoretical and practical knowledge.

The methodological intention sought with the TPD through the utilisation of the role-playing tool makes it easier for the student to contact and analyse the complex process that generates teaching practice, thus promoting a reflexive attitude in students. All of these actions relate not only to the professional dimension but also to the social and personal one (Castillo and Cabrerizo 2005b; Perrenoud 2004; Vázquez et al. 2001).

Furthermore, the proposal for the TPD aims to experiment on the interaction of the diverse dance practices. Results suggest that contact and action of learners with technical-dance registers other than those included in their basic training involve them in an interdisciplinary relationship that they experience from a body-related, didactic and reflexive perspective.

It can consequently be inferred that the social nature which permits the integration of classical, Spanish and contemporary techniques within the development of this proposal brings learners closer to consolidating critical thinking skills (Leijen 2009; Warburton 2002, 2004). It all favours their training development as teachers, promoting their awareness of the different forms and methodologies; technical-dance versatility or complementarity; and the acquisition of empathy and tolerance.

What advantages and drawbacks were detected after developing the TPD?

Thinking about the continuity of proposals like the present one leads us to focus our interest on identifying the advantages and drawbacks which had been detected by us while implementing the TPD.

The advantages highlighted in our TPD have been clearly shown through the answers to the previous questions. They revolve around the benefits and contributions that the proposal brings to participants thanks to its specific design and organisation. In other words, the TPD constituted a dynamic proposal which activated student participation and integrated the interaction of different dance options and techniques. It all projected from a reflection process located at the 'before', 'during', and 'after' stages of TPD implementation, which is in keeping with the proposals made by Perrenoud (2004) and Castillo and Cabrerizo (2005b). Therefore, the characteristics of this

structure, added to the positive willingness shown by participants are the true advantageous keys to this proposal. They additionally help learners' training in teaching practice, boosting the development of a reflexive professional attitude– processes required for the dance teacher's practice as suggested by Warburton (2002, 2004, 2008), Morris (2003), Burnard (2006) and Pimentel, Coutinho, and Guimarães (2009).

Nevertheless, the experience with this proposal made the participants detect a number of drawbacks after its implementation, some of them centred on the personal aspect (excessive workload) and others on TPD organisation aspects. It is important to highlight that none of these surfaces from the formative perception, something which becomes highly relevant for our proposal.

After cross-checking the results, it is possible to conclude that, despite the meticulousness identified in its design, and the development difficulties identified in some respects, the participants finally made a positive assessment of the TPD.

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